

Title: A simple of black holes, the EHT image of 2019 and a little discussion about white holes"

Abstract: Black holes are the things that really got me into astronomy. I was always curious about how these things existed! What happens to the things or the stars that is digested by the black hole? How can NOTHING escape it? Is there any possibility that it is fake? But after the published pic of ETH image in 2019, every human being alive was shocked because it proved that black holes exist..!!

Introduction : Gotta be honest: Black holes literally feel unreal. Like how do they swallow stars, planets, asteroids and crazily, even light..!!

According to scientists, the published data, black holes are formed when two massive stars collapse together, which causes it to gain a great gravitational pull that it becomes able to swallow everything. Black holes themselves are invisible but we are able to see the bright gas surrounding them.

The ETH image : In April 2019, a picture was published that shattered every human being alive. Because in this month, the picture of the great black hole was published by the scientists. But later on it was confirmed that it wasn't taken by only one telescope...it was taken by many telescopes which are revolving around the Earth.

Do white holes exist: personally, I really believe that white holes do exist. Because, in this massive multiverse, there's way too many things beyond our imagination to explore things, which makes me think that things like that might exist somewhere too!!! Because it ain't real that black holes really digest it bahaha!